

Chemical constituents of *Phyllanthus maderaspatensis* Linn.

Renuka Jain^{a*}, Gauri Chitale^a and Satish C. Jain^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

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Chromatographic separation of the insolubles and pet. ether solubles from the ethanolic extract of *Phyllanthus maderaspatensis* (whole plant) afforded *n*-tetracosane, taraxeryl acetate, ester of β -sitosterol, taraxerol, hexacosane, 32-methyltrtriacontanol-1, heptacosanol-14, 11-hydroxyhexacosan-3-one, tetracos-20(en)-1,18-diol, β -sitosterol and oleana-11,13(18)diene-3 β ,24-diol.

Phyllanthus maderaspatensis Linn. (Family : Euphorbiaceae) is an annual herb found in the arid zones of India. It exhibited antispasmodic action in isolated guinea pig ileum and anticancer, CNS depressant and hypoglycemic effects in mice¹. As there is no systematic study on this species except some preliminary work, reporting fatty acid and amino acid composition of the seed oil²; hence we have undertaken the present investigation.

The plant, *Phyllanthus maderaspatensis* Linn. was collected from the outskirts of Alwar (Rajasthan) and carefully identified in the Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur (Herbarium Sheet No. RUBL 4262). The air dried and finely powdered whole plant (3.5 kg) was exhaustively extracted with ethanol on a steam bath for 8 $\times$ 3 h. This extract (10.0 L) was concentrated to about 500 ml under reduced pressure and kept overnight at room temperature when a light green solid deposited at the bottom. The mother liquor was removed by decantation and the solid was washed with ethanol to afford the residue (R-1, 10.0 g). The mother liquor on removal of ethanol afforded a dark brown semi-solid (80.5 g) which was extracted with pet. ether. The pet. ether fraction on evaporation under reduced pressure gave a viscous brown concentrate (R-2, 30.5 g). Column chromatography of R-1 and R-2 over silica gel on elution with solvents of increasing polarity afforded compounds 1-4 and 5-11 respectively. The compounds were characterized on the basis of comparative spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR) and mass fragmentation pattern. The EIMS spectra were recorded on a Jeol D-300 mass spectrometer.

n-Tetracosane (1) : Elution with pet. ether afforded a white solid (0.32 g) which was crystallized as white flakes (EtOAc), m.p. 50–52°C, C₂₄H₅₀ (M⁺ 338).

Taraxeryl acetate (2) : Pale yellow solid eluted with pet. ether : C₆H₆ (3 : 2) was crystallized as white crystals (C₆H₆, 0.81 g), m.p. 295–298°C (darkening at 280°C), C₃₂H₅₂O₂

(M⁺ 468)³. Alkaline hydrolysis afforded taraxerol, m.p. 284–285°C, identified by co-IR and co-TLC. Isomerisation with alc. HCl gave β -amyrin acetate, m.p. 238°C.

Ester of β -sitosterol (3) : Elution with pet. ether : C₆H₆ (2 : 3) afforded green residue which on crystallization gave white needles (CH₃OH, 0.42 g), m.p. 72°C. In IR spectrum it gave peaks at 1730 (C=O), 1640 (C=C), 1180 (O=C–O),

730 and 720 cm⁻¹ (doublet -(CH₂)_n- deformation, n > 4). Its alkaline hydrolysis afforded β -sitosterol and a long chain fatty acid.

Taraxerol (4) : Elution with pet. ether : C₆H₆ (1 : 4) afforded a white solid which was crystallized as white plates (CHCl₃-CH₃OH, 0.38 g), m.p. 280–282°C, C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426). Compound was confirmed by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 296–298°C, co-TLC and co-IR.

Hexacosane (5) : Elution with pet. ether and pet. ether : C₆H₆ (4 : 1) afforded a white waxy material which on crystallization gave white granules (EtOAc, 0.73 g), m.p. 56–58°C, C₂₆H₅₄ (M⁺ 366).

32-Methyl-1-tritriacontanol (6) : It was eluted with pet.

Note

ether : C_6H_6 (1 : 4) as a white solid which was crystallized as white needles (CH_3OH , 0.57 g), m.p. 75–77°C, $C_{34}H_{70}O$ (M^+ 494). Identified by preparation of acetate, m.p. 62–63°C⁴. A doublet at 1370 cm^{-1} due to $-C(CH_3)_2$ stretching in the IR spectrum and $[M^+-43, CH(CH_3)_2]$ peak in the mass spectrum indicated primary alcohol to be a branched one with isopropyl group at other end.

Heptacosanol-14 (7) : The waxy solid obtained from pet. ether : C_6H_6 (1 : 4) fraction on crystallization afforded white flakes (EtOAc, 0.44 g), m.p. 78–80°C, $C_{27}H_{56}O$ (M^+ 396). Appearance of base peak at 213 due to $C_{13}H_{27}CH=OH$ moiety indicated the symmetrical nature of the alcohol with $C_{13}H_{27}$ moiety on both sides of $-CHOH$. It formed an acetate, m.p. 60–62°C.

11-Hydroxyhexacosan-3-one (8) : Elution with pet. ether : C_6H_6 (1 : 4) afforded white microcrystals (CH_3OH , 0.66 g), m.p. 72–73°C. IR spectrum exhibited peaks at 3390 ($-OH$), 1730 ($C=O$) and 1135 ($C-O$) indicating it to be a hydroxy ketone. In the 1H NMR spectrum, two methyl groups appeared as a triplet at δ 0.90, methylene groups appeared as multiplets at δ 1.30 (40H) and δ 2.30 (4H), the latter being those attached to the ketonic group, the proton geminal to $-OH$ group appeared as a singlet at δ 3.90, this indicated the compound to be a saturated hydroxyketone with 26 carbon atoms. The position of the functional groups was established by its mass fragmentation pattern in which the molecular ion peak appeared at m/z 396 ($C_{26}H_{52}O_2$)⁵. Significant ion peaks at m/z 241 [$C_{15}H_{31}CHOH$]⁺, 211 [$C_{15}H_{31}$]⁺, 185 [$C_2H_5CO(CH_2)_7CHOH$]⁺ and 155 [$C_2H_5CO(CH_2)_7$]⁺ suggested that $-OH$ group is located at C-11; the base peak at m/z 57 [C_2H_5CO]⁺ and due to McLafferty rearrangement at m/z 72 [$CH_3COC_2H_5$]⁺ indicated the presence of ketonic group at C-3 (Scheme 1). The compound formed an acetate, m.p. 60–63°C and an oxime m.p. 97–98°C which are being reported for the first time.

Tetracos-20(en)-1,18-diol (9) : Elution with pet. ether : C_6H_6 (1 : 4), afforded a pale yellow waxy solid which gave white crystals (CH_3OH , 0.48 g), m.p. 62–63°C which decolorised bromine water. In the IR spectrum, peaks at 3420 (br, OH), 1640 ($C=C$), 1110 and 1050 ($C-O$) indicated it to be an unsaturated diol. In the PMR spectrum, a methyl group at δ 0.89, 19 methylene groups at δ 1.30, two broad singlets due to D_2O exchangeable protons at δ 2.36 and δ 2.60, a proton geminal to hydroxyl group at δ 3.60,

two hydroxymethylene protons at δ 3.32 and two protons attached to sp^2 hybridized carbons at δ 5.20 were observed. In the mass spectrum peaks at m/z 368 ($C_{24}H_{48}O_2$, M^+), 350 [$M-H_2O$]⁺, 337 [$M-CH_2OH$]⁺, 325 [$M-CH_3CH_2CH_2$]⁺, 300, 285 and 255 along with many peaks with uniform loss of 14 mass units further confirmed the nature of the compound (Scheme 1). It formed a diacetate, m.p. 50–53°C, M^+ 452⁶.

β -*Sitosterol* (10) : Further elution with C_6H_6 afforded a light yellow solid which on crystallization gave white needles (CH_3OH , 1.20 g), m.p. 135–137°C, $C_{29}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 414), confirmed by preparation of acetate, m.p. 126–127°C.

Oleana-11 : 13 (18)-diene-3 β ,24-diol (11) : Elution with C_6H_6 : EtOAc (1 : 3) afforded yellow solid which was crystallized as white needles ($CHCl_3-CH_3OH$, 0.64 g) m.p. 302–305°C, $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$ (M^+ 440)⁷. In IR spectrum, a broad peak at 3420 ($O-H$) and two peaks at 1052 and 1030 cm^{-1} ($C-O$) indicated presence of two hydroxy groups. Peaks at 1650 and 1610 cm^{-1} corresponded to the presence of a conjugated diene system and at 1400, 1370, 1270 and 1240 cm^{-1} were indicative of an oleanane skeleton in the compound⁸. It was further confirmed by preparation of diacetate derivative, m.p. 238–239°C⁷.

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